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Research Project

Influence of Hf and Ta on the oxidation behaviour of Nb

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1. Introduction

Particle accelerators are widely used in the field of physics from elementary particles to solid states. Superconducting materials are used in particle accelerators to create large continuous electric and magnetic fields for beam acceleration and manipulation. The superconducting magnets are used to steer the particles in the right direction. One of the material which is used as magnets in particle accelerators due to its superconducting property is Nb₃Sn [2].

The Large Hadron Collider (LHC), and the Future Circular Collider (FCC), require a high amount of magnetic field (10-16T) to operate [1]. In the Nb₃Sn research field, internal oxidation is used to improve the superconducting properties of Nb₃Sn whereas Ta and Hf are used as alloying elements in Nb [2]. Thus, the oxidation of Nb can happen. So, in this project, we used Ta and Hf as an alloying element in Nb to check the oxidation and investigate the results.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Crystal structure and properties of Nb

2.1.1. Nb

Nb is a body-centred cubic structure element from group 5 of the periodic table as shown in **Fig 1**, which has a melting point of about 2450°C [3] and a density of 8.57 g/cm³ [3]. There are four different charge states of Nb which can be found 0, 2+, 4+, and 5+ which are associated with the metallic phase of Nb, NbO, NbO₂, and Nb₂O₅ respectively [4].

Fig 1: Cubic crystalline structure of Nb [4]

The phases, which have an O content between those of Nb and NbO (named NbO_x , NbO_y , NbO_z), are known as metastable phase whereas NbO, NbO_2 and Nb_2O_5 are known as stable phases [4]. The Nb – O system can be better understood from the phase diagram in Fig 2. Here it can be seen how different phases of oxides are formed by varying the percentage of O.

Fig 2: Nb – O phase diagram [4,5]

2.1.2. NbO

NbO has a NaCl crystal structure with Nb being located at the face centres and O at the edge centres [4,6], as illustrated in **Fig 3**. The density of NbO is 7.3 g/cc and the melting point is 1940°C which is lower than that of pure Niobium, Below the critical temperature ($T_c \approx 1.38\text{K}$) it becomes superconductive [4,12].

Fig 3: Crystal structure of NbO [4]

2.1.3. NbO₂

The next phase in the Nb-O is NbO₂. NbO₂ has a melting point of 1901°C and its density at room temperature is calculated to be 5.9 g/cm³ [4]. NbO₂ can be obtained by controlled oxidation of Nb or NbO, or else by the reduction of the Nb₂O₅ phase [4,8]. The NbO₂ has a distorted tetragonal structure with a rutile-type sublattice, which is illustrated in **Fig 4**. This is also characterized as NbO₆ octahedrons edge-sharing chains, which are cross-linked with one another by sharing corners [4]. At a temperature range of 797-808°C semiconductor metal–transition appears where it changes its crystal structure into a rutile lattice shown in **Fig 4(b)** as NbO₂ undergoes a reversible second-order phase transition [4].

Fig 4: Structure of (a) tetragonal NbO_2 and (b) rutile NbO_2 . [4]

2.1.4. Nb_2O_5

The next phase in the Nb-O system is Nb_2O_5 which is considered to be the most thermodynamically stable state of the system [4]. There are several polymorphic forms of Nb_2O_5 , which appear to be in white colour whether it is in powder form or transparent in the crystals [4]. In some cases, Nb_2O_5 can appear also as an amorphous phase [4]. From the currently available works of literature, there are different nomenclatures of the polymorph's phases of Nb_2O_5 and have not been studied well known [4]. In **Fig 5** the polymorph of Nb_2O_5 is shown.

Fig 5: One polymorph of Nb_2O_5 : The monoclinic structure of the so-called H- Nb_2O_5 phase [4].

2.2 Temperature reactions of Nb during the oxidation process at different temperatures.

When Nb is heated at higher temperatures in an O-containing atmosphere, it undergoes some reactions at different temperature ranges. The following are the reactions which occur in Nb during the heating process:

Firstly at 250°-400°C the reaction with O starts. O is adsorbed at the Nb surface where anion diffused to the coherent oxide layer already formed parabolic growth of Nb₂O₅ can be observed [7]. Then at the next temperature range of 400°-450°C, the oxide layer will reach its limit of thickness because of the high-volume ratio between the oxide and the Nb. The scale cracks will keep the thickness of the oxide layer virtually constant [7]. Then at the next temperature range of 450°-600°C, the oxide surface does not have any more saturation with the adsorbed O because it has reached the limit of saturation, which will reduce the temperature dependence on the oxidation rate [7]. There will be the conversion of amorphous Nb₂O₅ to α-Nb₂O₅ accompanying density change (it increases from 4.36 to 5.7 g/cm³ at room temperature) resulting in the decomposition of the outer scale into powders [7]. Then at above 550°C the rate, at which O diffuses from the oxide to the underlying metal also increases, which results in producing oxides with fewer anions [7].

Then at the higher temperature range i.e., from 600° to 675°C, the surface area, adsorption per unit area, and therefore the oxidation rate decreases with increasing temperature [7]. Then in the final temperature range from 675°-850°C there will be no control of the surface concentration of O by the adsorption [7].

Now, if we introduce alloying elements into the Nb, like Ta or Hf in our case, then the oxidation behaviour of the Nb may vary in several ways for example, there will be alteration in the diffusion rates, phases other than Nb₂O₅ are formed, there will be a change in the plasticity, and mostly there will be a change in the lattice parameters, which in turns changes the volume ratio [7].

2.3. Crystal structure and properties of Ta and Hf

Ta belongs to group 5 in the periodic table same as Nb. Ta also has body centred cubic structure; its melting point is higher than that of Niobium, meaning around 3000°C [3]. Whereas Hafnium belongs to group 4 in the periodic table, it has a melting point of about 2200°C, taking about its crystal structure it has different structures at different temperatures as Hf forms only one oxide i.e., hafnia (HfO₂) it forms stable monoclinic structure till the temperature range of 1700°C and above this temperature, it forms tetragonal structure [9].

2.3.1. Oxidation of Tantalum

Tantalum when it is heated in O containing atmosphere, forms an oxide such as Ta₂O₅ [10]. Ta can get oxidized easily, the O concentration increases with the increase in temperature and the thickness of the oxide layer increase with the increase in time according to some literature. At the temperature of 300°C, it first forms a suboxide of Ta₂O₅ then it is converted into stoichiometric Ta₂O₅, at a temperature of around 500°C [10]. When talking about the oxide thickness in relation to oxidation time, it is found that when oxidation time is increased then the thickness is also increased, if a graph is plotted between them then a parabolic curved is formed [10]. The initial thermal oxidation of pure Ta can be viewed as the interstitial dissolving of O into a Ta matrix that then leads to a saturated matrix, which is followed by oxide formation [10]. But if the Ta is oxidized at a higher temperature around 1390°C it forms into β-Ta₂O₅ [11]. The overall oxidation reaction [10] of the Ta can be described as follows:

3. Oxidation of Hafnium

As it is already described Hafnium forms only one oxide i.e., hafnia (HfO₂) [9]. This formed oxide will be stable in a monoclinic crystal structure up to the temperature range of 1700°C and then it will form a tetragonal crystal structure [9]. **Fig 6.** shows the oxidation curve of Hf at 350°- 800°C. It shows the relation between time and weight gain at different temperatures.

Fig 6. Hf oxidation in the temperature range of 350-800°C [9].

4. Experimental methods

In order to investigate the influence of Hf and Ta on the oxidation behaviour of Nb, heat treatment experiments were carried out. Pure Nb and alloys according to the overall composition of Nb₉₀Ta₁₀, and Nb₉₀Hf₁₀ were used as substrates to carry out the investigation.

The Nb metal and Nb alloy substrates to perform the experiment was measured to be of an average size of 5.20×8.25×1.00 mm (length × width × thickness). The front side of the substrate was grinded to ensure comparable surfaces. Then samples were cleaned with ethanol and weighed. After weighing, the samples were placed into an alumina crucible and then introduced for the heat treatment process in an electric furnace. After finishing the heat treatment, the samples were removed and allowed to cool down at room temperature for some time. Then, they were weighed again to check for the mass gain obtained due to oxidation. Later, microstructural, and chemical analysis investigations were done by using XRD, SEM and EPMA.

Heat treatment

The heat treatment was carried out to check the influence of O on the pure Nb along with Nb-Ta and Nb-Hf alloys. The samples were heated at different temperatures and different time periods in an electric furnace. The furnace was always preheated before placing the sample. The samples were heated at 400°C, 600°C and 800°C respectively between 0.5h and a maximum of 336h.

X-ray diffraction

After the heat treatment process only one sample per temperature and alloy was investigated, the samples were taken to perform some qualitative phase analysis by XRD. For that, some of the formed oxide layer was ground to a powder. For XRD analysis a D8 Advance diffractometer by Bruker was utilized. 40 kV and 30mA created the required Co-K α -1 radiation from the X-ray source.

The samples were investigated using the Bragg-Brentano geometry. To index the given data, the Rietveld method integrated into the software TOPAS was used.

Scanning electron microscopy and EDX

For SEM imaging a JSM-7800F from JEOL with an accelerating voltage of 20 kV and probe current of 35 nA was used. Backscattered electrons were used to get the orientation and element contrast modes, they allow for a local phase differentiation. After the embedding, the samples were ground and polished down to 0.04 μm . Between the preparation steps, the cross sections were controlled to ensure a regular grind/polish pattern and avoid deep scratches. Just before analysing the samples, they were covered with vaporized C to ensure sufficient conductivity and counteract charging phenomena that would create unnecessary artefacts.

Electron backscatter diffraction

EBSDF gives us the analysis of crystal structure and orientation. In this method electrons are diffracted into lattice planes and it is recorded in the form of Kikuchi pattern, which will provide us the information about crystal structure and orientation. An accelerating voltage of 20 kV and probe current of 35nA was utilized.

The software used for EBSDF pattern acquisition and EDX spectrum acquisition was TEAM from EDAX and for EBSDF pattern analysis it was TSL OIM Analysis from EDAX.

Electron probe microanalysis

For EPMA analysis the equipment JEOL JXA-8230 SuperProbe was used which was operated at 10 kV voltage and 40 nA current, and calibration was performed on pure element standards from ASTIMEX. To investigate the exact O content in the substrate close to the surface and the amount of dissolved Ta respective Hf in the Nb₂O₅.

5. Results

1. Mass gain results

After performing the heat treatment, mass gain values were obtained. These were obtained by calculating the mass difference before and after the heat treatment for each sample and dividing this with the corresponding sample surface area. From these values, it can be analysed, how much the samples have been oxidized at different temperatures and time duration.

Fig 7(a): Mass gain results at 400°C

Fig 7(b): Mass gain results at 600°C

Fig 7(c): Mass gain results at 800°C

Figs. 7 (a) (b) and (c) show the mass gain results at 400°C, 600°C and 800°C respectively. At 400°C it is observed that mass gain by Nb is greater than Nb-Ta after 96 hours of heating. Nb has been oxidized more compared with Nb-Ta, whereas Nb-Hf does not get oxidized more oxidised compared with Nb-Ta after 336 hours of the firing. At first, Nb-Hf was kept for heat treatment for up to 96 hours but there was no change in oxide layer formation was observed, so then it was continuously kept under heat treatment for up to 336 hours, which showed a little increase in mass gain.

At 600°C mass gain of Nb is observed to be lower than Nb-Ta after a 24h time period. Nb-Ta has been oxidized more than Nb when the temperature is increased to 600°C. This can be because of the easy oxidation of Ta. When Nb-Hf was heat treated for 24h it did not show any sign of oxidation and therefore there was no mass gain. At a longer time, there is a decrease in the mass gain value of Nb-Hf this may be due to the formation of volatile oxide or else due to inappropriate weighing. **(See Fig 7. b)**

Fig 7(c) shows us the mass gain results, which are obtained at 800°C. The heat treatment was done for up to 4h and Nb-Ta was found to have been oxidized more compared with others. Whereas Nb did not oxidise much but Nb-Hf oxidized slightly higher than Nb because it depends on the surface area of the sample. As it is seen in **Fig 7(c)**. the mass of Nb got reduced after 2h, this can be due presence of some volatile component which caused the mass loss when kept for more than 2h for heat treatment.

Results of samples at 400°C

The structural investigations are carried out to determine the phases present, the amount of O dissolved in the sample and the amount of alloying elements dissolved in the formed oxides. The XRD results from the sample investigations showed that the common and major phase present is Nb_2O_5 for all substrate materials. **Fig 8** shows the XRD result obtained when Nb-Ta was oxidized at 400°C.

Fig 8: XRD result of Nb-Ta at 400°C

The phase Nb_2O_5 is present in the sample by a total amount of 99.12% and the remaining came from the Nb-based substrate below. In the SEM and EDX analysis, it shows that the oxide layer forms on top of the substrate and the alloying elements are present in the oxide. EDX was performed to qualitatively distinguish between oxide and substrate. The substrate layer consists of 90% Nb and 10% of O in the pure Nb sample which was heat treated at 400°C for 96h. whereas in the oxide layer it was 65% Nb and 35% O. The results of the Nb-Hf samples shows different values, Nb-Hf when oxidized at 400°C for 336h the substrate layer has 78% Nb, 12% Hf and 9% O whereas the oxide layer was 60% Nb, 11% Hf and 28% O. This result shows us the difference in the percentage of elements in the oxide and substrate layer, which means more amount of O is not dissolved inside the substrate when compared with oxide. It formed another layer on the top, which is the oxide layer. The EPMA results show the O content in the sample. For Nb, when the analysis was done in the substrate far away from the oxidized surface, there was no O present or dissolved. Close to the oxide layer, there was 4-5% of O dissolved in it and in the oxide layer around 30 % (mass%) of O was present at 70 % (atomic%) which means that EPMA indicates that Nb_2O_5 phase is present. For the Nb-Ta sample

around 1% of O was dissolved in the top of the substrate and 32% of O in the oxide layer. But also, the presence of Ta is also investigated in the layers, in the substrate close to the oxide Nb to Ta ratio was found to be 81:19 (mass %) and in the oxide layer the ration between them is 59:14 (mass%).

In the Nb-Hf sample heat-treated at 400°C on EPMA investigation a different percentage of O and Hf was dissolved in the substrate and oxide. The O content is low, it is around 2.5% at the top of the substrate but in the oxide layer, it is around 32%. Coming towards the mass presence of Hf in the sample, the Hf is dissolved till the bottom of the substrate with 14-15% mass percentage in the bottom of the substrate and 12-13% in the oxide layer. The Nb to Hf ratio in the substrate near to the oxide is 81:13 (mass %) and the ratio in the oxide layer is 64:13 (mass %).

Fig 9: SEM image of a) Nb at 400°C b) Nb-Ta at 400°C and c) Nb-Hf for at 400°C

The EBSD analysis gave images of the phases present in the oxide and substrate layers. Nb₂O₅ was the dominant phase found in all the samples, other than this NbO and NbO₂ were found in the samples.

Overall, in XRD investigations, it is found that Nb_2O_5 is the common phase present in all the samples. The SEM and EBSD results also confirm the same phases present. The EPMA results showed the O content present in the oxide and substrate layer. Nb and Nb-Ta have less O content in the oxide layer when compared with Nb-Hf. The O content in terms of mass % is more Nb-Hf sample when compared with the other two at this temperature.

Results of samples at 600°C

The XRD investigations of samples at 600°C found to have the same phase present in the sample i.e., Nb_2O_5 but along with a few other phases such as NbO and NbO_2 for different samples. The samples of pure Nb had almost Nb_2O_5 phases when XRD results of the different heating time periods were analysed. For the sample of Nb-Ta, it was recorded that the 1h heat-treated sample also has a Nb_2O_5 phase and the 24h heat-treated sample had 99% of Nb_2O_5 and the remaining 1% was just Nb. It can be observed that keeping the Nb-Ta samples for more time for heat treatment increases the formation of the Nb_2O_5 phase. The Nb-Hf samples also show the same formation of the Nb_2O_5 phase but in different percentages over the time period. For 1h of heating, it was 30% Nb_2O_5 and 70% Nb, whereas for the 24h time period it is 26% Nb_2O_5 and 73% NbO.

Fig 10: EBSD of Nb-Ta at 600°C for 24h shows the formation of the NbO phase

The SEM analysis of these samples was also carried out. In the Nb sample heated for 24h the dominant phase was Nb_2O_5 followed by small amounts of

NbO. **Fig 11.** shows the EBSD phase map of the sample. In the fig, the yellow colour represents the NbO phase in the sample, the blue background represents the Nb₂O₅ phase and the green area is Nb. In the sample Nb-Hf which was heat-treated for 96h, it did not show any oxides formed on the top of the substrate area. There was only the Nb phase present as shown in **Fig 12.**

Fig 11: EBSD of Nb at 600°C for 24h

Fig 12: SEM image of Nb-Hf at 600°C for 96h shows no oxides formed

According to XRD investigations, it is found that at this temperature the sample Nb-Hf has formed less amount of Nb_2O_5 phase i.e., only 26% whereas in the Nb-Ta sample there is more amount of Nb_2O_5 phase present. This is because in the Nb-Hf sample the material did not undergo full oxidation which lead to less amount of phase formed.

Results of samples at 800°C

The XRD investigations are also carried out for the samples at 800°C to find out the phases formed in the samples at this temperature.

Fig 13: XRD of Nb-Hf at 800°C for 1h

The XRD results of Nb-Hf show us that the phase formed at this temperature is 100% Nb₂O₅ as shown in **Fig 13**. At temperature, no other phase was formed in the sample, only the Nb₂O₅ phase is present. Similar to this, Nb-Ta also form only the Nb₂O₅ phase at this temperature. So, in order to obtain the Nb₂O₅ oxide phase it can be said that heating the Nb alloys at 800°C for a 1h time period may form this phase in all cases.

The EBSD results of Nb display the formation of Nb₂O₅ in the sample along with small traces of NbO close to the substrate shown in **Fig 14**. The Nb-Hf (**Fig 15**) and Nb-Ta samples show only the Nb₂O₅ phase present in the sample.

Fig 14: EBSD image of Nb heat treated at 800°C for 1h showing NbO phase present

In the EPMA analysis of Nb heat-treated at 800°C, the O content in the sample was investigated. There was no O content in the substrate of the sample, but in the oxide layer, there was around 35% (mass%) of O present. In the Nb-Ta

sample, there was almost no O in the substrate far away from the oxide formed. But in the top layer of the substrate, there was around 15-30% (mass%) of O dissolved in it and in the oxide layer around 32% (mass%) of O is present.

In the Nb-Hf sample, there was 10-20% (mass%) of O in the substrate close to the oxide layer and 10-15% (mass%) of Hf dissolved in it. Whereas in the oxide layer the amount of O dissolved is 15-33% (mass%) and a maximum of 15% Hf by mass is present in the oxide layer of the sample.

So, overall, the XRD investigations show that at this temperature Nb_2O_5 phase is present in all the samples. The SEM and EBSD analysis also indicate the same phase is present. The EPMA results show the amount of O (in mass %) present in the samples in the oxide layer is almost 30-35%.

Fig 15: EBSD image of Nb-Hf heat treated at 800°C for 4h does not show any phases at the boundary.

6. Conclusion

The aim of this experiment was to investigate the O influence in Nb and Nb alloys, which were subjected to heat treatment to find out the phases present in the samples. The mass gain values after heat treatment and the amount of dissolved O were also investigated using different methods such as XRD, SEM, EBSD, and EPMA.

The experiment showed the mass gain values of the different alloys along with Nb when heat treated at different temperatures. Nb-Ta showed the highest mass gain values at all temperatures except at 400°C, Nb-Hf has no mass gain when heat-treated at 600°C for 24h, and at 800°C Nb showed the lowest mass gain value.

In the XRD analysis, we found out the phases present in the samples by the peaks available. NbO, NbO₂ and Nb₂O₅ are the phases which are present in the samples but Nb₂O₅ is the dominant phase in all cases. The time period of heat treatment of the samples and the temperature affect the number of phases that can be formed in the sample. At 800°C Nb-Hf and Nb-Ta showed 100% of the Nb₂O₅ phase present in them, this is also shown in SEM investigations. Lattice parameters of the Nb₂O₅ phase in all the samples were also analysed. The parameters were the same in all the samples it was a=6.17Å, b=29.17Å, and c=3.93Å belonging to the space group Pbam.

In SEM and EBSD investigations it was determined the number of phases present, and the places at which the phase is present or not. The results show the images of the oxide and particular phases present in the oxide by EBSD mapping. From this investigation, there was a Nb₂O₅ phase found in all the samples.

In the EPMA investigations, the amount of O, Ta and Hf dissolved in Nb and Nb₂O₅ was investigated. At 400°C the O content was found to be around 30% (mass%) which indicates the presence of Nb₂O₅ and the Nb: Ta ratio and Nb: Hf both in the oxide and substrate layer was also calculated in all the samples to determine how much of the alloying elements were dissolved in the oxide layer. At 800°C the EPMA results showed the O content was around 30-33%(mass%) in the oxide layer and a maximum of 15% (mass%) of Hf was found in the Nb-Hf sample.

Overall, from the experiment carried out and from the results, it can be said that Nb-Hf alloy showed a good oxidation resistance. The influence of Hf on the Nb is the reason why oxidation can be improved. Moreover, the influence of O and Hf on the Nb can be used to improve the superconducting properties of the Nb alloys it can be because of its better oxidation resistance when compared with Nb-Ta and the phases it forms. More research can be done in the specific field which will bring more improvements in the material.

7. References

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Declaration of Originality

I confirm that the submitted student's thesis is original work and was written by me without further assistance. Appropriate credit has been given where reference has been made to publications or texts as well as imagery of others.

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